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Crop management

Effect of planting time, lopping, and N fertilization on growth and yield of traditional rice variety C14-8 in the Andaman Islands, India

S. Singh, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Port Blair 744101, India

Despite several high-yielding rice varieties being introduced in the Andaman Islands of India, local rice

variety C14-8 occupies more than half of the rice area. The variety is tall, highly photoperiod-sensitive, and has a very long maturity period. Farmers lop the foliage once or twice during the vegetative phase to prevent the crop from lodging. Leaves are used as green fodder. We studied how planting time, lopping, and N fertilization affect the growth and yield of C14-8.

Thirty-day-old seedlings of C14-8 were transplanted in prefertilized (NPK)

cement pots (30 × 30 × 30 cm) during the first weeks of Aug, Sep, and Oct 1992 and third weeks of Jun, Jul, Aug, and Sep 1993. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design with five replications. Plants in a set from each planting date (except the last one) were lopped 50 d after transplanting. Half of the lopped plants were fertilized with N at 5 g urea/pot and the other half were left unfertilized. Another set from each planting date received no treatments.

Effect of planting time, lopping, and N fertilization on growth, yield, and yield attributes of local rice cultivar C14-8. Andaman Islands, India. 1992-93 wet seasons.

Date of planting vs lopping	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/pot (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Economic yield (g/pot)	Biological yield (g/pot)	Harvest index (%)	Leaf area/plant (dm ²)	Leaf area/tiller (cm ²)	Dry wt./tiller (g)	N uptake (g/pot)	N harvest index (%)	N use efficiency (g/g N)	Days to flowering
<i>1992 wet season</i>															
Planting in 1st wk Aug															
Normal	180	41	119	24.6	25.0	112.0	417.5	26.8	108	253	10.2	3.32	44	33.7	145
Lopping without N	174	23	101	25.6	25.0	72.1	195.4	37.5	50	208	8.4	1.70	54	42.4	145
Lopping with N	178	34	115	25.2	23.0	92.7	335.1	28.0	87	251	9.8	2.97	39	31.2	145
Planting in 1st wk Sep															
Normal	165	41	134	26.3	13.5	131.3	398.8	33.1	73	192	9.7	3.16	49	41.5	140
Lopping without N	157	37	78	26.2	19.3	73.2	236.0	31.4	59	172	6.4	1.62	49	45.2	140
Lopping with N	160	38	116	26.0	12.0	120.2	344.7	34.8	72	189	9.1	2.68	44	44.8	140
Planting in 1st wk Oct															
Normal	152	43	122	25.8	7.5	132.7	331.0	40.8	64	185	7.9	3.00	60	44.5	135
LSD at 5%	3	7	18	N5	5.8	26.4	57.1	4.8	16	21	1.6	0.52	4	3.5	3
<i>1993 wet season</i>															
Planting in 3rd wk Jun															
Normal	177	45	120	26.5	28.3	136.1	615.0	22.2	123	243	13.6	3.86	47	35.2	180
Lopping without N	157	26	118	27.0	21.0	84.4	254.6	33.3	82	234	9.8	1.50	62	56.2	180
Lopping with N	165	32	106	27.8	17.4	89.2	297.6	30.1	88	251	9.3	1.95	63	45.7	180
Planting in 3rd wk Jul															
Normal	164	36	131	26.4	19.3	118.4	400.0	29.6	61	149	11.1	2.50	62	47.5	160
Lopping without N	147	32	103	27.8	19.3	84.8	254.6	33.4	38	154	8.0	1.50	67	67.0	160
Lopping with N	150	30	121	26.0	16.0	94.2	268.2	35.0	52	163	8.9	1.81	77	52.0	160
Planting in 3rd wk Aug															
Normal	174	41	147	27.5	14.8	164.5	543.0	30.0	58	149	13.4	3.27	63	50.1	140
Lopping without N	141	26	100	28.2	15.2	70.5	207.5	34.0	30	125	8.0	1.24	60	56.4	140
Lopping with N	151	37	86	27.1	19.0	92.0	255.0	36.0	55	177	7.0	1.84	71	50.0	140
Planting in 3rd wk Sep															
Normal	166	51	113	26.8	13.4	151.7	439.6	34.5	102	257	8.6	3.17	65	47.8	132
LSD at 5%	10	6	28	1.7	8.2	26.5	86.7	4.5	20	27	2.8	0.85	6	4.5	7

Most of the growth and yield characters were recorded at maturity, except for leaf area character, which was recorded at flowering stage.

Delayed planting caused significant reduction in growth parameters (plant stature, biological yield, leaf area/plant, leaf area/tiller, dry weight/tiller, and N uptake) but improved grain yield/pot because of the large increase in grains/panicle and panicles/pot, greater reduc-

tion in spikelet sterility, and greater harvest index, partitioning of N, and N use efficiency (see table).

Lopping the foliage during the vegetative phase (50 d after planting), however, depleted both growth and yield characters (stature, biological yield, leaf area/plant, leaf area/tiller, panicles/pot, and grains/panicle). Fertilization following lopping, however, markedly improved almost all growth and yield

characters associated with productivity, resulting in higher grain yield/pot than lopping without applying N.

Time to maturity was reduced drastically by delaying planting until August. Grain yield could be improved substantially by transplanting C14-8 in the last week of August or the first week of September. Cutting leaves followed by 20-30 kg N/ha in early planted crops improved the productivity of C14-8. ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Relationship between farmers' early- and late-season insecticide sprays

K. L. Heong and A. A. Lazaro, IRRI

One of the objectives of farmers in using insecticides is to avoid yield losses due to insect pests. Thus, the number and timing of these sprays reflect farmers' perceptions of the expected impact of insecticides on production. We used farmer survey data sets from Leyte and San Jose, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, and the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, to analyze the relationship between farmers' early-season sprays and their late-season sprays.

Interview surveys using the same questionnaire were carried out in Leyte in 1990, the Mekong Delta in 1992, and San Jose in 1994. Farmers were asked to recall the timing of insecticide sprays used in the previous season. We categorized sprays applied in the first 40 d after crop establishment as early sprays and those applied later than 40 d as late

sprays. The survey data were tabulated into a 2 × 2 contingency table using these two variables (Table 1). Each cell contained the frequency of occurrence of the respective attributes. We used the Pearson χ^2 test for independence to determine the association between spray early and spray late. The null hypotheses was that the two variables, spray early and spray late, are independent.

The expected frequencies for each cell from each survey site were determined by calculating the frequencies expected if no association between the two variables existed. The larger the discrepancy between these expected values and the observed values, the larger the degree of association and thus the higher the value of Pearson χ^2 (Table 2).

We used Pearson χ^2 values adjusted for a 2 × 2 contingency table to test for significance. The values were significant in all three surveys. Thus, we rejected the null hypothesis in all cases and concluded that early sprays are closely associated with late sprays.

Table 2. Tests of independence between early- and late-season insecticide use and probabilities of farmers' spray patterns at 3 sites in the Philippines and Vietnam.

Statistics	Leyte	San Jose	Mekong Delta
n	300	285	685
df	1	1	1
χ^2	62.2	36.7	4.2
P	<0.01	<0.01	0.04
Spray pattern	Leyte	San Jose	Mekong Delta
Early and late	0.71	0.75	0.61
Early only	0.08	0.17	0.21
Late only	0.09	0.02	0.12
No sprays	0.11	0.06	0.06

We obtained the predicted probabilities of occurrence in each case of the contingency table for the three sites. At all sites, the probability of a farmer spraying both early and late was much higher than the probabilities of the other cases occurring (Table 2), meaning farmers who tended to spray insecticides early tended to spray late as well.

While the analysis may indicate significant association between early and late sprays, it does not provide any information on cause and effect. Farmers who sprayed both early and late may be risk averse, those who tend to use higher inputs, or those who are economically better off.

Research has shown that most early insecticide sprays are unnecessary and may be avoided. Emphasis to reduce early insecticide use may have the added value of reducing late insecticide use as well. ■

Table 1. Frequency of early- and late-season insecticide sprays by rice farmers in Leyte and San Jose, Philippines, and the Mekong Delta, Vietnam.

	Location	Farmers (no.)		Total
		Spray late	Do not spray late	
Spray early	Leyte	213	24	237
	San Jose	215	49	264
	Mekong Delta	415	142	557
Do not spray early	Leyte	28	35	63
	San Jose	5	16	21
	Mekong Delta	84	44	128
Total	Leyte	241	59	300
	San Jose	220	65	285
	Mekong Delta	499	186	685